

Supplementary Information

Sensitive period for the plasticity of alpha activity in humans

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subject	gender	age (Y)	Degree of visual impairment	diagnosis

1	M	0.06	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
2	M	0.44	severely impaired	Optic nerve hypoplasia
3	M	0.86	severely impaired	Ocular albinism
4	M	1.04	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
5	F	1.2	severely impaired	Nystagmus
6	F	1.23	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
7	F	1.34	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
8	F	1.34	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
9	M	1.45	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
10	F	1.48	totally blind	Nystagmus
11	M	1.65	totally blind	Ocular malformation
12	F	1.66	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
13	M	1.83	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
14	M	2.17	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
15	F	2.32	severely impaired	Ocular malformation
16	M	2.61	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
17	F	2.65	severely impaired	Ocular albinism
18	M	2.76	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy

19	F	3.55	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
20	F	3.66	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
21	F	3.7	severely impaired	Nystagmus
22	F	3.8	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
23	F	3.84	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
24	M	3.87	severely impaired	Optic nerve hypoplasia
25	M	4.24	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
26	M	4.29	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
27	F	4.62	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
28	M	4.78	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
29	F	4.95	severely impaired	Optic nerve atrophy
30	F	4.99	severely impaired	Optic nerve hypoplasia
31	F	5.08	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
32	M	5.14	severely impaired	Nystagmus
33	F	5.35	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
34	M	5.44	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
35	M	5.65	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
36	F	5.66	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy

37	M	5.83	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
38	M	6.1	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
39	F	6.1	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
40	F	6.26	totally blind	Optic nerve hypoplasia
41	M	6.31	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
42	F	6.33	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
43	F	6.51	severely impaired	Congenital cataract
44	M	6.53	severely impaired	Nystagmus
45	F	6.72	totally blind	Retinopathy
46	M	6.76	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
47	F	6.91	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
48	M	7.29	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
49	F	7.35	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
50	M	8.64	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
51	F	8.79	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
52	M	8.97	severely impaired	Optic nerve hypoplasia
53	F	9.07	totally blind	Congenital cataract
54	M	9.47	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy

55	M	9.47	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
56	F	9.55	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
57	M	9.56	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
58	M	9.6	severely impaired	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
59	M	10.31	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy
60	F	10.47	totally blind	Inherited congenital retinal dystrophy

Supplementary Table 1. Details about the group of 60 totally blind/severely impaired children (BSI, with 36 totally blind individuals) considered in the study. In the first column the subject number; in the second column the subject gender; in the third column the subject age expressed in decimal years (i.e. age in days / 365); in the fourth and in the last columns respectively, the degree of visual impairment and the diagnosis evaluated by the clinicians of IRCCS Mondino Foundation, Pavia, Italy.